

Evaluation of Serum Stromelysin-2 as a Potential Biomarker for Subclinical Atherosclerosis in Hypothyroid Patients

Evaluación de la estromelisin-2 sérica como posible biomarcador de aterosclerosis subclínica en pacientes hipotiroideos

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Abstract

Background: Hypothyroidism is a medical condition that happens when the thyroid fails to produce enough thyroid hormone to keep up with the requirements of the body's metabolism. Hypothyroidism that is not treated can result in a variety of serious health complications, including hypertension, dyslipidemia, atherosclerosis, and others. Subclinical atherosclerosis is a form of atherosclerosis that occurs when a patient has atherosclerotic plaque but no clinical symptoms of the disease. Stromelysin-2 have an inflammatory effect, released by macrophages in response to a wound or an inflammatory stimulus.

Objectives: Measure serum stromelysin-2 levels in people who have clinical and subclinical hypothyroidism to predict an increased risk of atherosclerosis and find the correlation between stromelysin-2 and the lipid panel.

Materials and Methods: In this study, there were 130 participants. They were classified into three groups. We measured serum stromelysin-2 levels and lipid profiles.

Results: There is a significant rise in the mean value of serum stromelysin-2 ($P=0.001$), total cholesterol, ($P=0.001$), triglycerides ($P=0.001$), LDL-C ($P=0.001$), VLDL-C ($P=0.001$), risk ratio of TC/HDL-C ($P=0.001$), risk ratio of LDL-C/HDL-C ($P=0.001$), atherogenic coefficient ($P=0.001$) and atherogenic index of plasma ($P=0.001$) with significant diminish of serum HDL-C ($P=0.001$) in clinical and subclinical hypothyroid patients compared to healthy controls.

Conclusion: Patients with clinical and subclinical hypothyroidism had higher levels of serum stromelysin-2, higher levels of castelli risk index, atherogenic index of plasma and atherogenic coefficient were found in patients could be used as more accurate risk predictors of cardiovascular disease. Moreover, significant positive correlation was found between Stromelysin-2 and lipid panel.

Keywords: Hypothyroidism, Subclinical Atherosclerosis, Stromelysin-2, lipid panel, atherogenic.

Resumen

Antecedentes: El hipotiroidismo es una afección médica que ocurre cuando la tiroides no produce suficiente hormona tiroidea para satisfacer las necesidades del metabolismo del cuerpo. El hipotiroidismo que no se trata puede provocar una variedad de complicaciones de salud graves, como hipertensión, dislipidemia, aterosclerosis y otras. La aterosclerosis subclínica es una forma de aterosclerosis que ocurre cuando un paciente tiene placa aterosclerótica pero no tiene síntomas clínicos de la enfermedad. La estromelisin-2 tiene un efecto inflamatorio, liberado por los macrófagos en respuesta a una herida o un estímulo inflamatorio.

Objetivos: Medir los niveles séricos de estromelisin-2 en personas que tienen hipotiroidismo clínico y subclínico para predecir un mayor riesgo de aterosclerosis y encontrar la correlación entre la estromelisin-2 y el panel de lípidos.

Materiales y Métodos: En este estudio hubo 130 participantes. Fueron clasificados en tres grupos. Medimos los niveles séricos de estromelisin-2 y los perfiles de lípidos.

Resultados: Hay un aumento significativo en el valor medio de estromelisin-2 sérica ($P = 0,001$), colesterol total ($P = 0,001$), triglicéridos ($P = 0,001$), LDL-C ($P = 0,001$), VLDL-C. ($P = 0,001$), índice de riesgo de CT/HDL-C ($P = 0,001$), índice de riesgo de LDL-C/HDL-C ($P = 0,001$), coeficiente aterogénico ($P = 0,001$) e índice aterogénico del plasma ($P = 0,001$) con una disminución significativa del HDL-C sérico ($P = 0,001$) en pacientes con hipotiroidismo clínico y subclínico en comparación con controles sanos.

Conclusión: Los pacientes con hipotiroidismo clínico y subclínico tuvieron niveles más altos de estromelisin-2 sérica, se encontraron niveles más altos de índice de riesgo de Castelli, índice aterogénico del plasma y coeficiente aterogénico en los pacientes que podrían usarse como predictores de riesgo más precisos de

enfermedad cardiovascular. Además, se encontró una correlación positiva significativa entre Stromelysin-2 y el panel de lípidos.

Palabras clave: Hipotiroidismo, Aterosclerosis Subclínica, Stromelisin-2, panel lipídico, aterogénico.

ber of studies have concluded so far that a rise in serum stromelysin-2 levels is linked to both overt and subclinical atherosclerosis. Moreover, stromelysins-2 are released and secreted by humans' atherosclerotic plaques¹⁰.

Introduction

Hypothyroidism is a medical condition that happens when the thyroid fails to produce enough thyroid hormone leads to a slowing down of numerous metabolic processes¹. Hypothyroidism that is not treated can result in a variety of serious health complications, including hypertension, dyslipidemia, atherosclerosis, infertility, cognitive impairment, and neuromuscular dysfunction². The concentration of TSH is widely regarded as the most sensitive indicator of hypothyroidism in individuals who are not experiencing acute illness³.

Subclinical atherosclerosis is a form of atherosclerosis that occurs when a patient has atherosclerotic plaque but no clinical symptoms of the disease⁴. Atherosclerosis refers to an artery's hardening because of an accumulation of fat, lipid-rich plaque embedded in the intima of the vessel wall⁵. Hyperlipidemia increases the risk of premature atherosclerosis and ischemic heart disease⁶.

Thyroid disorder, appearing as either clinical or subclinical hypothyroidism, adversely variations in lipid metabolism, which causes hypercholesterolemia, which gradually raises the chance of developing heart disease and potentially mortality. Decreased low-density lipoprotein (LDL) receptor activity is the primary cause of hypercholesterolemia in hypothyroidism. In hypothyroidism, dyslipidemia is caused by a change from a high rate of degradation to synthesis, with increased of LDL-C⁷. Dyslipidemia then results from a rise in serum triglyceride (TG), very low-density lipoprotein-cholesterol (VLDL-C), and low-density lipoprotein-cholesterol (LDL-C) and a reduction in high density lipoprotein-cholesterol (HDL-C) levels. Lesions in the endothelium of the vessels led to atherosclerosis⁸.

Three ratios to predict cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk: the atherogenic index of plasma (AIP), the castelli's risk index (CRI), and the atherogenic coefficient (AC). These fractions can be used in clinical settings to assess CVD risk, in addition to the lipid profile⁹.

Stromelysins belong to the matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) subfamily; stromelysin-2 is the most important one, also known as MMP-10. Stromelysin-2 have an inflammatory effect, released by macrophages in response to a wound or an inflammatory stimulus. A num-

Materials and methods

In this study, there were 130 participants ranging in age from 23 - 70 years were selected from the Iraqi population, collected between October 2022 to January 2023. All participants agreed after being informed. The College of Medicine/University of Baghdad's Ethical Committee approved the research. They had been divided into three groups: group A consisted of 45 patients diagnosed with clinical hypothyroidism; group B included patients with subclinical hypothyroidism; and group C included 42 healthy individuals used as controls.

The diagnosis of primary hypothyroidism is according to clinical symptoms and signs, physical examination, and blood test represented by increased TSH and normal or abnormal free T3 and free T4.

Biochemical tests including serum stromelysin-2, was determined using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) developed by Elabscience in the United States of America and lipid profiles by (Cromatest) including (TC, TG, and HDL-C), were measured biochemically. While the following equations were used to measure VLDL-C, LDL - C, AIP, CRI-I, CRI-II and AC:

$$VLDL-C = TG / 5$$

$$LDL-C = TC - (LDL-C + HDL-C)$$

$$AIP = \log (TG / HDL-C)$$

$$CRI-I = TC / HDL-C$$

$$CRI-II = LDL-C / HDL-C$$

$$AC = (TC - HDL-C) / HDL-C$$

AIP readings less than 0.11 are associated with a low risk of CVD, whereas those between 0.11- 0.21 and greater than 0.21 are associated with moderate and high risks, respectively¹⁶.

Statistical analysis:

The data was measured using SPSS-25, which refers to the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, version 25. The information is given as a mean, a range,

and a standard deviation. The ANOVA test was used to find out how important differences between different means (quantitative data). Two quantitative variables were analyzed using Pearson's correlation with t-test was used to find of the correlation between parameters. Statistically significant value, the P-value needed must be equal or less than 0.05.

There is a significant rise in the mean value of serum TC (P=0.001), TG (P=0.001), LDL-C (P=0.001), VLDL-C (P=0.001), AIP (P=0.001), AC (P=0.001), risk ratio of TC/HDL-C (P=0.001), risk

ratio of LDL/HDL-C (P=0.000) and stromelysin-2 (P=0.001) with a significant decrease in the average value of HDL-C (P=0.001) in hypothyroid patients as compared with

Using Pearson's method for analyzing correlations, As shown in Figure 1, we found that stromelysin-2 levels were positively correlated with TG (r=0.349, P=0.019), AIP (r=0.36, P=0.014), AC (r=0.342, P=0.021), and TC/HDL-C ratio (r=0.342, P=0.021).

Figure 1: (a) Positive correlation between serum Stromelysin-2 and TG levels (r= 0.349, P= 0.019); (b) Positive correlation between serum Stromelysin-2 and AIP (r= 0.36, P= =0.014); (c) Positive correlation between serum Stromelysin-2 and AC (r= 0.342, P=0.021); (d) Positive correlation between serum Stromelysin-2 and TC/HDL-C ratio (r=0.342, P= 0.021).

Parameters	Studied Groups			P - Value*
	Group A Mean ± SD	Group B Mean ± SD	Controls Mean ± SD	
TC (mg/dl)	208.4 ± 30.4	194.7 ± 15.9	158.3 ± 22.9	0.001
TG (mg/dl)	199.6 ± 38.5	188.9 ± 13.1	117.4 ± 22.9	0.001
HDL-C (mg/dl)	42.33 ± 10.72	45.63 ± 12.17	53.01 ± 8.62	0.001
LDL-C (mg/dl)	126.1 ± 26.8	111.3 ± 22.9	81.85 ± 21.8	0.001
VLDL-C (mg/dl)	39.93 ± 7.70	37.79 ± 2.62	23.48 ± 4.59	0.001
AIP	0.67 ± 0.15	0.63 ± 0.13	0.34 ± 0.11	0.001
AC	4.03 ± 1.69	3.51 ± 1.60	1.27 ± 0.62	0.001
TC/HDL-C	5.03 ± 1.69	4.51 ± 1.61	2.27 ± 0.62	0.001
LDL/HDL-C	3.23 ± 1.26	2.76 ± 1.37	1.61 ± 0.61	0.001
Stromelysin2(ng/ml)	1.85 ± 0.30	1.24 ± 0.18	0.75 ± 0.07	0.001

* A significant difference between three or more means (using the ANOVA-test) at the 0.05 significance level.

Table 1: Comparison of mean levels of biochemical parameters between studied groups

Hypothyroidism is a progressive hormonal disorder with an impact on the cardiovascular system that progresses from mild subclinical to clinical manifestation. Dyslipidemia is one of the most significant cardiovascular risk factors in hypothyroidism. There are numerous causes of atherosclerosis in hypothyroid patients, including dyslipidemia, an increase in artery stiffness, problems with endothelial function and obesity¹¹. In developing countries, heart disease is the most common cause of death. Lipid abnormalities were known risk factor. Diabetes, metabolic syndrome, thyroid disorders, and obesity are all factors that contribute to dyslipidemia. Decreased HDL, increased TC, LDL-C, and TC aggravate atherosclerosis. Thyroid dysfunction has an adverse effect on the lipid profile¹². Dyslipidemia is an abnormal lipid level in the blood caused by abnormal lipoprotein metabolism and is a risk factor for CVD. Because dyslipidemia and atherosclerotic vascular changes begin in childhood and adolescence, early detection and management of dyslipidemia may help prevent atherosclerosis and CVD later in life¹³. A recent scientific investigation revealed that more fat in the body was associated with different dangers and causes of death in patients with coronary artery disease (CAD), classified according to the coexistence of left ventricular hypertrophy or not¹⁴.

The present study showed that clinical and subclinical hypothyroid patients had a higher lipid panel represented by (TC, TG, VLDL-C and LDL-C) as compared to the control group. This result is similar to a recent study by Aruna and her followers, which showed that dyslipidemia which may increase the danger of the progression of cardiovascular disease¹⁵.

This study also showed that HDL-C is significantly decrease in the clinical and subclinical hypothyroid groups than the control group. This study agrees with previous studies that showed that low HDL-C levels and defective HDL function are common lipid disorders that have a major impact on the progression of atherosclerotic and cardiovascular disease¹⁶. Elevated TC, TG, and LDL-C levels and reduced HDL-C contribute to the progression of atherosclerosis¹⁷. Moreover, previous research has shown that hypothyroidism corresponds to a lower HDL-C level. The inverse relationships between atherosclerotic risk and concentrations of HDL-C and its constituent apoprotein A1 are well known¹⁸.

The plasma atherogenic index is an important indicator that can be used on its own to estimate the chance of heart disease or as an aid to the individual lipid profile. AIP can be used as a diagnostic tool when all the other risk factors for atherosclerosis look normal¹⁹. The current study showed that mean levels of AIP significantly

higher in clinical and subclinical hypothyroid patients compared with the controls, similar to Akici and colleagues who showed that ALP is higher in patients with hypothyroidism to predict the risk of CVD²⁰. In addition, a long-term study found that AIP value increases with increasing CAD risk and that AIP is a marker that has a very high sensitivity to variations in lipoprotein profiles between the families of people who had a premature myocardial infarction and those who didn't²¹.

According to this study, clinical and subclinical hypothyroid patients had significantly higher mean levels of AC, CRI-I and CRI-II when compared with controls, similar to other studies by Akici and colleagues²¹. CRI-I, CRI-II, AIP and AC could be used as more accurate risk indicators of cardiovascular disease²². There were reports that lipid ratios could have a more comprehensive explanation than individual lipid measures, even TG or HDL-C²³. These ratios could be a better reflection of the metabolic and clinical interactions between lipid fractions and can give information about risk factors that are hard to measure with routine analyses²⁴. However, an early study postulated that using either CRI-I or CRI-II is a better choice than TC or LDL-C alone since almost two-thirds of the cholesterol in the blood found in LDL-C, and it has been shown that the predictive power of their ratios is higher than that of the single parameters²³.

The present study also showed that clinical and subclinical hypothyroid patients had significantly higher stromelysin-2 levels relative to the control group. This agrees with Chen and parents' study, which showed that stromelysin-2 levels rise in patients with hypothyroidism to predict the risk of atherosclerosis²⁵. It has been clearly shown that higher levels of stromelysin-2 are related to the development of coronary calcifications in individuals who have subclinical atherosclerosis¹⁰. Previous study demonstrates a substantial correlation between a higher level of stromelysin-2 and subclinical atherosclerosis²⁶. This supports the findings of Orbe and his followers, who discovered that elevated serum stromelysin-2 levels are linked to carotid plaques, higher carotid IMT, an indicator of atherosclerosis's early stages, and systemic inflammatory markers²⁷.

Patients with clinical and subclinical hypothyroidism had higher levels of serum stromelysin-2, a matrix metalloproteinase being produced by macrophages in response to injury or inflammatory stimuli, which might be a potential marker for prediction of atherosclerosis. Additionally, higher levels of AIP were found in patients which considered as a risk marker to assess CVD even when other lipid parameters show normal levels. Also, higher levels of CRI, CRII, and AC in patients could be used as more accurate risk predictors of CVD. Moreover, significant positive correlation was found between Stromelysin-2 and lipid panel which reflect as association between stromelysin-2 and risk factors of CVD.

Conflict of interest

No known conflict of interest correlated with this publication.

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